

THE ROLE OF USING MODERN APPROACH AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11298566>

Abstract: The article discusses the conditions for the use of modern innovative technologies in the educational process. The article discusses some issues of using innovative technologies to increase the effectiveness of the educational process. The article focuses on the modern aspects of the further development of science in Uzbekistan, the education of young people with deep knowledge, high spirituality and culture, the effective use of digital technologies in the formation of a competitive economy, and the training of personnel in this field.

Key words: interactive methods, innovative education, innovation, pedagogical technology, information technology, traditional education.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются условия использования современных инновационных технологий в образовательном процессе. В статье рассматриваются некоторые вопросы использования инновационных технологий для повышения эффективности образовательного процесса. В статье акцентировано внимание на современных аспектах дальнейшего развития науки в Узбекистане, воспитании молодых людей с глубокими знаниями, высокой духовностью и культурой, эффективном использовании цифровых технологий в формировании конкурентоспособной экономики, подготовке кадров в это поле.

Ключевые слова: интерактивные методы, инновационное образование, инновации, педагогические технологии, информационные технологии, традиционное образование.

Annotatsiya: Maqola ta'lim jarayonida zamonaviy innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanishning shart-sharoitlari haqida fikr-mulohazalar yuritilgan. Maqolada ta'lim jarayoni samaradorligini oshirishda innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanishning ayrim masalalari muhokama qilingan. Maqolada O'zbekistonda ilm-fanni yanada rivojlantirishning zamonaviy jihatlari, chuqur bilim, yuksak ma'naviyat va madaniyatga ega yoshlarni tarbiyalash, raqobatbardosh iqtisodiyotni shakllantirishda raqamli texnologiyalardan samarali foydalanish va bu sohada kadrlar tayyorlashga alohida e'tibor qaratadi.

Kalit so'zlar: interaktiv metodlar, innovatsion ta'lim, innovatsiya, pedagogik texnologiya, axborot texnologiyalari, an'anaviy ta'lim.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the interest and attention to the use of interactive methods, innovative technologies, pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day, one of the reasons for this is that until now, traditional education If in the school, students are taught to acquire only ready-made knowledge, modern technologies teach them to search for the acquired knowledge by themselves, to study and analyze independently, and even to draw conclusions by themselves. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the development, formation, learning and education of a person, and at the same time performs the functions of management and guidance.

Today, educational, social, economic, in general, all spheres are gradually being transferred to the digital economy. The most important of these is the field of education. Because the education system must be updated every day. The reason is that the lessons built on the basis of modern approaches will not be ignored by any student. Therefore, many psychologists and scientists have conducted a number of experiments in this regard. It is known that a student of any age as long as his attention is focused on one place for twenty minutes and he can receive information only during this time.

METHODS

In the process of education, the student becomes the main figure. Therefore, modern teaching methods - interactive methods, innovative technologies have a great role in training qualified professionals in higher educational institutions and faculties. Knowledge, experience and interactive methods of pedagogic technology and pedagogic skills ensure that pupils-students have an educated, mature qualification.

Innovation (English innovation) is innovation. Innovative technologies are innovations and changes in the pedagogical process and the activities of teachers and students, and in its implementation mainly interactive methods are fully used. Interactive methods are called group thinking, that is, they are methods of pedagogical influence and are a component of the educational content. The uniqueness of these methods is that they are implemented only through the joint activity of the teacher and the student.

Modern educational development has brought a new direction - innovative activity to the field. By the 21st century, which is considered to be the age of information - highly developed technologies, the attention to the issue of wide introduction of innovation in the educational process has increased. In Uzbekistan, in recent years, innovation has entered the education system as one of the first compared to other fields, and we can see how innovation is reflected in the educational process in the following. The entry of innovation into the system of pedagogical sciences was determined by the following.

- a) Gender pedagogy;
- b) Heuristic pedagogy;
- c) Compulsory pedagogy;
- g) Androgical pedagogy

- We see the introduction of active, passive and interactive methods of innovation into teaching methods. If the use of the active method serves to increase the activity of students in the course of the lesson, the passive method is explained by giving students a one-sided understanding. The interactive method is understood as active action together (teacher and student, student and student).

- We can see the introduction of innovation into the form of lessons in the example of standard, non-standard and virtual lesson forms.

- There are types of innovation in teaching types: problem-based learning, heuristic learning, graded learning, integrated learning, interactive learning, informal learning, formal learning, non-formal learning.

- Multimedia, electronic boards and other tools can be used as an example of innovation in teaching tools.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Innovation in teaching methods can be seen in the following methods.

1. Active method - encourages students to be active during the lesson, to think and reflect on a certain situation and reality.
2. Passive method - leads to the formation of a one-sided understanding of the studied subject in students during the lesson.
3. Interactive method. The purpose of this method is based on the joint active behavior of the teacher and students during the lesson.

We can see the innovation of the lesson in the following form.

- a) Standard lesson - the structure of the lesson does not change.
- b) Non-standard lesson - the structure within the lesson changes.
- c) Virtual lesson - i.e. distance learning. The concept of "new" occupies a central place in pedagogical innovation. It also arouses interest in special, conditional, local and subjective innovation in pedagogical science.

According to V.A. Slastenin, the private innovation, the current modernization envisages updating one of the elements of a specific system product. Conditional innovation is a combination of certain elements that lead to complex and progressive innovation. Innovation is a tool: a new method, methodology, technology, etc. V.I. Zagvyazinsky defined the new concept and said that the new in pedagogy is not just an idea, but approaches, methods, and technologies that have not yet been used, but the elements of the pedagogical process are combined or taken separately, and effectively fulfill the tasks of education and upbringing in changing conditions and situations. represents the advanced beginnings of the solution. Pedagogical innovation is the process of developing, implementing, testing and evaluating innovations in the field of education that help to effectively achieve these goals. Among them: the educational process changes over time, the labor market makes new demands on future employees, and teaching is changed, adapted to new goals, new pedagogical methods, methods and methods are needed to achieve this. .

Active use of advanced pedagogical technologies in the educational process, improvement of educational efficiency, analysis and introduction into practice is one of the important tasks of today. It is extremely important to develop students' thinking, consciousness, worldviews, to turn them from free listeners to free participants. The teacher should be the leader in the lesson, and the students should become participants. In achieving this task, the superiority of innovative activity brings multifaceted effects.

Innovations in education help to achieve the following goals:

Humanization, democratization of the educational process;

Activation of students' cognitive activity;

Improving the effectiveness of the organization of education and training;

Changes of educational material from the point of view of methodology and didactics.

An approach to education is a set of basic principles, requirements, and goals that form the basis for new technologies.

The requirement of modern education is not to give students as much knowledge as possible, but to teach them to learn on their own, not only to know, but also to be able to work with the received information.

Pedagogical innovations are based on two main approaches:

A student-centered approach involves directing the educational process to each individual student. Modern pedagogy should take into account the unique experience and

character of each student, develop his individuality and talent. Implementation of this approach includes reliance on the principles of choice (students can choose the fields they want), trust (absence of authoritarian pressure from teachers), creativity and success, subjectivity, individuality;

CONCLUSION

In short, innovative technologies, interactive methods and modern pedagogical technologies used in the educational process play a key role in the proper formation of the relationship between the teacher and the student and in the proper organization of training. is of primary importance.

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